

DIGITAL LITERACY IN ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES TEACHING

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Abstract

The digital age has redefined all spheres of human life across the globe. Accordingly, developments in ICT have become an integral part of effective practices in the language classroom. The mainstream of language teaching provides ample evidence to support the claim that these technological innovations can help foster language learning in various ways. Yet, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is considered as a significant area of English Language Teaching (ELT) that has been affected by digital facilities. Based on the curriculum requirements, the ESP course has to address university students' occupational needs for their future careers. Since the potential of digital literacy in ESP context is repeatedly acknowledged in literature, teachers are required to be digitally competent in inducing instructional technology in order to develop professional effectiveness. The need for inducing technology in all educational institutions is unavoidable due to the development of digital culture in society as one of the main indicators of effective education. However, successful adaptation of digital culture in foreign language teaching depends on the level of digital competencies that are necessary for adaptability in the digital space. Regarding the field of ESP in higher education, teachers are expected to be able to use recent digital devices; active use of such technologies for communication and digital understanding of the principles of action in the digital space. In respond to the worldwide demand of the mastery of English in various specialisations, digital literacy is prerequisite for enhancing the efficacy of ESP teaching. Therefore, digital skills as content have to be fully mastered by foreign language teachers in general and ESP teachers in particular. The modern world has established new requirements for education and the ability to use digital tools to facilitate communication, the search for knowledge and scientific information. Educational institutions should actively use digital integration in the field of ESP teaching in order to meet the demands of the modern world. For successful implementation of such promising prospect, it is essential to understand the benefits of technological knowledge of teachers who are the real and prime implementers of ICT in their pedagogical practices. This paper considers the development of digital literacy for ESP teachers not only in terms of possession of technological tools, but also takes into account their positive attitude to employ them in the language classroom. In this regard, it focuses on the importance of the development of the required skills to use digital content, which is necessary to provide sufficient access to the digital world and achieve efficiency and motivation for ESP learning. As new technologies already penetrated aspects of pedagogy, the present paper attempts to raise educational authorities' awareness about the importance of providing ESP teachers with proper training that should address digital literacy skills needed for successful adaption in the digital space. This paper suggests that there are different modes of teaching that can enhance student's engagement and increase their motivation to learn English. This can happen only when ESP instructors are equipped with adequate knowledge and skills which allow them to systematically embed digital modes of delivery in the ESP syllabus. This paper describes the ways in which digital literacy can enhance teachers' ability to better manage ESP teaching in higher education.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, ESP Teaching, pedagogical practices, digital skills